

suspension was administered orally 30 min prior to commencement of the experiment. The measured quantity of milk was offered in cavity blocks and milk intake was recorded after 60 min. Increased milk consumption (compared with control) in treated groups was taken at criterion of anxiolytic activity of the compounds.

Results and Discussion

The ALD_{50} of compounds 1-4, 9 and 10 was >1000 mg/kg i.p., for 8 and oxazepam it was 825 mg/kg i.p., and 5 had an ALD_{50} of 681 mg/kg i.p. At 1/5th ALD_{50} none of the compounds showed any effect on gross behaviour while oxazepam produced depressant effect. Compound 5 afforded 80%, 4, 7 and 10 showed 20%, and oxazepam produced 100% protection against metrazole induced seizures. 3 and oxazepam showed 20% and 80% protection, respectively against supra-maximal electroshock seizures. In addition 4 and oxazepam increased the milk consumption in non-fasted rats by 30% and 58%, respectively. Other compounds were devoid of this activity. Mean milk ingestion for control group was 5.16 ± 0.625 ml while for 4 and oxazepam it was 6.80 ± 0.415 and 8.2 ± 2.2 ml, respectively.

These results had suggested that enzymatic hydrolysis of terminal amide linkage was occurring and the acetamido linkage was found to be very facile among the amide linkages studied. Lesser activity among higher homologues (7 and 8) has led to the conclusion that formation of an 8- or 9-membered ring was not favoured. Thus, 2-[N'-substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone with terminal acetamido linkage might be acting as the prodrug form of 1,4 benzodiazepines.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Prof. V. S. Misra, Head, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, for facilities, and to Dr. Nityanand, Director and Prof. B. N. Dhawan, Deputy Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for bioassay facilities.

References

1. A. A. SINKULA and S. H. YALKOWSKY, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, 64, 181.
2. C. H. HASSAL, S. W. HOLMES, W. H. JOHNSON, A. KROHN, C. E. SMITHEN and W. A. THOMAS, *Experientia*, 1977, 33, 1492.
3. R. B. DAVIS and L. C. PIZZINI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1884.
4. S. C. BELL, J. S. SULKOWSKI, C. GOCHMAN and S. J. CHILDRRESS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 562.
5. H. J. HORN, *Biometrics* 1956, 12, 311.
6. R. A. TURNER in "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 28.
7. E. A. SWINYARD, W. C. BROWN and L. S. GOODMAN, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1952, 106, 319.
8. S. J. CHILDRRESS in "Burger's Medicinal Chemistry", ed. M. E. WOLFF, 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1981, Part III, p. 982.
9. M. NAKANISHI, H. YASUDA and T. TSUMAGARI, *Life Sci.*, 1973, 13, 467.
10. B. P. H. POSCHEL, *Psychopharmacologia*, 1971, 19, 193.

Flavonoidic Constituents of *Rhus wallichii* Hook.f. (Anacardiaceae)

(Miss) FEHMEDA KHATOON, M. KHABIR
and

W. H. ANSARI*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 26 November 1984, revised 10 May 1985,
accepted 31 July 1985

SINCE the report of the isolation and characterisation of some novel biflavonoids¹ from *Rhus succedanea*, the genus *Rhus* has become the focus of attention for investigation in this field. In the present paper we report the isolation and identification of a biflavone together with flavonols and flavonol glycosides from the leaves of *Rhus wallichii* Hook.f. (Anacardiaceae). The co-occurrence of a biflavone with the flavonols and flavonol glycosides is the first example in *Rhus* genus.

Fresh leaves procured from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari (Nepal), after thoroughly de-fattening by repeated extraction with light petroleum ether and benzene were extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue left was treated successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, chloroform and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate fraction was chromatographed over silica gel column and five flavonoidic compounds, A, B, C, D and E were obtained.

Compound A: The compound eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave +ve Shinoda test, and was identified as kaempferol by comparison of its m.p. (276-78°), m.m.p., co-tlc and pmr data with the authentic sample.

Compound B: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2), and was crystallised from acetone-methanol (1 : 1) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, formed an acetate $C_{25}H_{20}O_{12}$, m.p. 197-98°, and was characterised as quercetin by comparison of m.p and pmr data of its acetate with the authentic sample.

Compound C: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (7 : 3), m.p. 254-56°, and was characterised as amentoflavone by comparison of its R_f value (0.16) (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5), characteristic fluorescence of its methyl ether (bright yellow) in uv light², and pmr data of its acetate with the authentic sample^{3, 4}; τ ($CDCl_3$) 1.99 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-2'), 2.05 (1H, q, J 3 and 9Hz, H-6'), 2.52 (2H, d, J 9Hz, H-2''', 6'''), 2.56 (1H, d, J 9Hz, H-5'), 2.96 (2H, d, J 9Hz, H-3''', 5'''), 2.76 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-8), 3.10 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-6), 3.00 (1H, s, H-6''), 3.30, 3.35 (1H each, s, H-3, 3''), 7.54, 7.60, 7.78, 7.75, 7.90, 7.98 (18H, 6 OAc).

Compound D and E eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 7) were separated and purified by repeated column chromatography on polyamide using water-methanol as the eluent.

Compound D: It was crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 185-86°. It was analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{11}$, gave green ferric reaction, orange-red Shinoda test and positive Molisch test. The uv spectra of the compound, λ_{max} (MeOH) 253 and 370 nm, showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis with 6% sulphuric acid gave an aglycone, which was identified as quercetin by chromatographic and spectral comparison with an authentic sample. The aqueous part on working up for sugar showed the presence of rhamnose by co-pc with authentic rhamnose on Whatman No. 1 (butanol-acetic acid-water, 4 : 1 : 5 organic layer, R_f 0.33; butanol-ethanol-water, 4 : 1 : 2.2, R_f 0.36). Aniline hydrogen phthalate was used as the spraying reagent and the spots were developed by heating at $\sim 110^\circ$. Thus compound D is a monorhamnoside of quercetin. Hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside gave quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether which with $AlCl_3$ showed a bathochromic shift from 361 to 420 nm, thereby indicating that the rhamnose moiety was present at the 3-position⁵. Thus compound D was identified as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside (quercitrin).

Compound E: It was crystallised as yellow needle-shaped clusters, m.p. 235-36°, analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12} \cdot H_2O$. It gave an olive green colouration with $FeCl_3$, orange-red Shinoda test and a positive Molisch test. Its uv spectrum showed maxima at 254 and 370 nm indicating the compound to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone which was identified as quercetin and the sugar was identified as glucose by co-pc. Thus the compound is a mono-glucoside of quercetin. The pmr spectrum of its acetate taken in $CDCl_3$ showed signals due to four phenolic acetyls at τ 7.57 (3H), and 7.69 (9H), and four alcoholic acetyls at 8.87 (6H), 8.04 (3H) and 8.12 (3H). The signals over the range 4.4-6.2 account for the seven protons of the glucosyl residue. One of these, a doublet centred at 4.87 was assigned to the $C_{1''}$ proton, the large coupling constant (J 7 Hz) due to *trans*-diaxial with the $C_{2''}$ proton indicated the presence of β -configuration. The A-ring protons at 6- and 8-positions appeared as doublets at 3.3 (J 2.5 Hz) and 2.79 (J 2.5 Hz), respectively. The B-ring protons formed an ABX pattern characteristic of 3', 4'-oxygenated flavonoids. The 2'-proton showed up as a doublet at 1.98 (J 2.5 Hz), while 5'- and 6'-protons appeared as doublet at 2.7 (J 9 Hz) and quartet at 2.12 (J 2.5 Hz and 9 Hz), respectively. Compound E was thus characterised as quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucoside.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.K.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. FA-CHING CHEN and YUE-MEET LIN, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, 14, 1644 and references therein.
2. K. K. CHEKAL, B. K. HANDA and W. RAHMAN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, 48, 284.
3. A. PELTER, R. WARREN, N. HAMEED, N. U. KHAN, M. ILYAS and W. RAHMAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 1897.
4. A. PELTER, R. WARREN, K. K. CHEKAL, B. K. HANDA and W. RAHMAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 1625.
5. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer-Verlog, New York, 1970, p. 53.

Direct Determination of Mercury in Complex Compounds

T. PAL

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

Manuscript received 6 December 1984, revised 30 April 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

MERCURY(II) has been maximum cation deformability among the metal ions of the same group in the periodic table. Thus it is not surprising to find more organic ligands forming thermally stable chelates with mercury(II) in comparison to Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} . Mercury(II) has been determined using precipitants containing nitrogen and oxygen^{1,2}. Among those reagents benzoylacetacetanilide and benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide need special mention. Those are not effective for the direct determination of mercury(II) from its coordinated compounds. The reagent acetylacetothioacetanilide, used in the present investigation easily precipitates HgS from the solutions of simple or chelated compounds of mercury. No drastic degradation³ of mercury chelates is necessary. HgS is very stable. Hence, if discarded as such, it will not pollute the atmosphere. Use of thioamide requires the hydrolysis of the reagent either in alkaline or acidic solutions (Willgerodt reaction⁴) for the homogenous precipitation of HgS . Moreover, simple thioamides cannot precipitate HgS from the experimental solution containing chelated Hg^{II} ion. In some cases thioanilide forms complexes⁵ without giving sulphide ion. Hence in this report, acetylacetothioacetanilide (AATA) has been suggested as a HgS -precipitating agent.

Experimental

Acetylacetothioacetanilide [$CH_3CO.CH(CH_3-CO).CS.NH.C_6H_5$]: This reagent was prepared in the laboratory following the reported method⁶. Equimolar phenylisothiocyanate was mixed with sodium salt of acetylacetone. When the reaction was complete, the product was extracted with cold water and acidified. The solid thus separated was